

Interview Reference Material

Protocol 1: Schema & Data Model Validation

DPP Interoperability Platform — Practitioner Interview

*This handout accompanies the interview and provides reference material.
You may annotate it freely or refer back to it at any time during our discussion.*

1 Project Context

The **DPP Interoperability Platform** is an open-source prototype that addresses two problems in Digital Product Passport (DPP) ecosystems:

1. **Identifier fragmentation:** Products carry identifiers from different standards (GTIN, VIN, serial numbers, DIDs, LGTINs) with no single resolution mechanism.
2. **Semantic heterogeneity:** Different DPP initiatives (Tractus-X, Battery Pass, CIRPASS) use incompatible data formats, field names, and serializations.

The platform resolves heterogeneous identifiers and normalizes initiative-specific payloads into a **Shared Core Schema (v0.2)**: a product-agnostic core with modular, domain-specific extensions.

Key Terminology

Core Schema

The *product-agnostic* base fields (17 fields such as product ID, manufacturer, compliance). “Core” means common to all product types, not “mandatory” or “most important.”

Extension

A domain-specific module (e.g., Battery, Substances of Concern) that adds fields on top of the core. Each extension is **based on existing regulations and standards**—not invented from scratch.

SoC

Substances of Concern—chemical safety data required by REACH and RoHS regulations. Not “State of Charge” (which is a battery status field).

LCA-EF

Life Cycle Assessment / Environmental Footprint—carbon footprint and GHG emissions data following the GHG Protocol and EU PEF methodology.

DPP

Digital Product Passport—a structured, machine-readable dataset describing a product across its lifecycle (per EU ESPR Regulation 2024/1781).

JSON-LD

A W3C standard for embedding linked-data semantics in JSON. Allows the same data to serve both REST APIs and knowledge graphs.

Provenance

Metadata recording *where* each data field came from, *who* transformed it, and *how confident* the mapping is.

Gap

A field expected by the schema but absent in the source data—reported with severity rather than silently omitted.

Metric	Value	Detail
Test suite	512 tests	438 microservices + 74 UI, 100% pass
Identifier types	7	UUID, GTIN, VIN, Serial, MPN, DID, LGTIN
Adapters	4	Tractus-X + Battery Pass (JSON + JSON-LD each)
Extension modules	4	Battery, SoC, LCA-EF, Food
Initiative profiles	5	Tractus-X, Battery Pass, Core-Only, Food, All
Language / framework	TypeScript	Node.js + Next.js 16.1.6

2 Requirements for Validation

Why We Present These Requirements

The Shared Core Schema was designed to satisfy **29 requirements** extracted from DPP standards, EU regulations, and initiative technical artifacts (Tractus-X, Battery Pass, CIRPASS, GBA). This handout covers the **19 requirements** relevant to Protocol 1 (schema design, extensions, mappings, linked data, provenance, and coverage). **Your task:** review whether these requirements are **correct, complete, and appropriately prioritized**. Feel free to annotate the table—mark items you agree with (✓), disagree with (×), or flag as missing (?).

2.1 Schema Design (SC-00 – SC-04)

ID	Requirement	Implementation Summary	Your Note
SC-00	Build initial Shared Core Schema	v0.1 monolithic schema (~68 fields); validated and refactored in DSR iteration 1	
SC-01	Product-agnostic core schema v0.2	Minimal core with 17 product-agnostic fields (identification, manufacturer, product, lifecycle)	
SC-02	Per-field provenance & gap reporting	Provenance per field (source, actor, confidence, conversion rule); gap reporting with severity levels	
SC-03	Adapter lifecycle (parse-map-validate-report)	Adapter interface enforces lifecycle; initiative profiles compose core + selected extensions	
SC-04	Core + extensions contract	Extensions compose via JSON-LD context layering; validated by 512 automated tests	

2.2 Extensibility & Onboarding (EXT-01 – EXT-03)

ID	Requirement	Implementation Summary	Your Note
EXT-01	Adapter onboarding checklist	New adapters implement <code>AdapterInterface</code> and register via configuration; no core changes required	
EXT-02	Substances of Concern (SoC) extension	SoC extension: SVHC check, REACH/RoHS compliance, hazardous substance entries	
EXT-03	LCA / Environmental Footprint extension	LCA-EF extension: carbon footprint (GHG scopes 1–3), lifecycle stages, impact categories	

2.3 Mapping & Transformations (MAP-01 – MAP-03)

ID	Requirement	Implementation Summary	Your Note
MAP-01	Mapping specification format (CSV)	Two mapping CSVs: Tractus-X (43 rows), Battery Pass (45 rows)	
MAP-02	Unit conversion & normalization rules	Adapter methods handle unit conversions; conversion rules documented in provenance	
MAP-03	Reusable transformation library	Shared transformation helpers extracted into adapter base methods	

2.4 Linked Data & Semantic Web (LD-01 – LD-05)

ID	Requirement	Implementation Summary	Your Note
LD-01	JSON-LD context mapping	Five JSON-LD context files mapping to Schema.org, PROV-O, QUDT, Dublin Core	
LD-02	Adapter JSON-LD output	Both adapters support JSON-LD mode with embedded @context, @id, @type	
LD-03	Triple-store integration guide	TriplyDB integration with 7 DPPs (~900 triples), loading guide, SPARQL endpoint	
LD-04	SPARQL query demonstrations	12 SPARQL queries covering materials, carbon footprint, compliance, provenance	
LD-05	Extension RDF mapping pattern	Each extension has OWL vocabulary + JSON-LD context with stable IRIs on GitHub Pages	

2.5 Provenance, Coverage & Evaluation (PRV-01 – PRV-02, EV-02)

ID	Requirement	Implementation Summary	Your Note
PRV-01	Provenance schema (PROV-O)	Per-field provenance with source, actor, confidence; PROV-O in JSON-LD output	
PRV-02	Tamper-evidence & integrity checks	Content hashing approach documented; full implementation deferred to production	
EV-02	Coverage metrics & evaluation criteria	Data coverage score per module; gap reporting with populated/expected counts	

Validation Prompt

1. Are any of these requirements **unnecessary** or **incorrectly scoped**?
2. Are there **missing requirements** that you consider critical for DPP interoperability?
3. Which requirements would you **prioritize differently**?

3 Architecture Overview

4 Core Fields (17 Product-Agnostic Fields)

Core Schema v0.2 — Product-Agnostic Fields

These 17 fields apply to **any** Digital Product Passport, regardless of product domain. “Core” means *shared across all product types*, not “mandatory” or “most important.” Domain-specific data lives in extensions (Section 5).

Field	Required	Description
passportId	Yes	Canonical passport identifier (UUID or URI)
version	No	Schema version (e.g., “0.2.0”)
lastUpdated	No	ISO 8601 timestamp of last update
productType	No	Product category (battery, food, electronics, etc.)
productId	No	Product identifier (distinct from passport ID)
category	No	Product classification code
model	No	Product model name
brand	No	Brand name
manufacturingDate	No	ISO 8601 date of manufacture
manufacturingCountry	No	Country of manufacture (ISO 3166-1)
placingOnMarket	No	Date when the product was first made available on the EU market (per ESPR Art. 2)
manufacturer.name	No	Manufacturer legal name
manufacturer.id	No	Manufacturer identifier
manufacturer.facility	No	Manufacturing facility name
identifiers[]	No	Array of heterogeneous product identifiers
materials	No	Material composition overview
compliance	No	Summary of regulatory compliance declarations (e.g., CE marking, EU DoC references)

5 Extension Modules

Modular Extension Architecture

Each extension is independently versioned, defined as an OWL ontology with its own JSON-LD context. Extensions are **derived from existing regulations and industry standards** (EU Battery Regulation, REACH, GHG Protocol, EU FIC), not invented from scratch. New domains (textiles, electronics, construction) can be added without modifying the core.

5.1 Battery Extension v0.1

EU Battery Regulation 2023/1542 — Namespace:

<https://jorgerenatoleon.github.io/DPP-Interoperability-Microservices/vocab/battery#>

The battery extension uses **six nested sub-objects** rather than flat fields:

Sub-Object	Key Fields
chemistry	chemistryType, cellType, cathode, anode, electrolyte, composition
performance	ratedCapacity, nominalVoltage, powerCapability, energyRoundtripEfficiency, internalResistance, cycleLife
status	stateOfCharge, stateOfHealth, cycleCount, lastInspectionDate, condition
materials	criticalRawMaterials[] (name, mass%), recycledContent[] (material, recycled%)
durability	warrantyPeriod, expectedLifetimeYears, expectedLifetimeCycles, operatingTemperatureRange
circularity	dismantlingInfo, safetyInstructions, recyclingInstructions, sparePartAvailability

5.2 SoC Extension v0.1 (Substances of Concern)

REACH Regulation (EC) 1907/2006, RoHS Directive 2011/65/EU — Namespace:

<https://jorgerenatoleon.github.io/DPP-Interoperability-Microservices/vocab/soc#>

Field Group	Key Fields
substancesOfConcern[]	name, casNumber, concentration, unit, location, hazardClassification
svhcCandidateListCheck	lastChecked, result (PASS/FAIL), matchedSubstances[]
reachCompliance	Boolean: REACH registration satisfied
rohsCompliance	Boolean: RoHS substance restrictions met
lastComplianceAudit	ISO 8601 date of last compliance audit

5.3 LCA-EF Extension v0.1

GHG Protocol, ISO 14040/14044, EU PEF — Namespace:

<https://jorgerenatoleon.github.io/DPP-Interoperability-Microservices/vocab/lca-ef#>

Field Group	Key Fields
carbonFootprint	total (kgCO ₂ e), unit, perKwh, calculationMethod
ghgEmissions	scope1, scope2, scope3, total (GHG Protocol scopes)
lifecycleStages[]	Stage breakdown (raw materials, manufacturing, transport, use, end-of-life)
impactCategories[]	Environmental impact categories (acidification, eutrophication, etc.)

5.4 Food Extension v0.1

EU FIC Regulation 1169/2011 — Namespace:

<https://jorgerenatoleon.github.io/DPP-Interoperability-Microservices/vocab/food#>

Field Group	Key Fields
allergens[]	Allergen name, severity, regulatory basis
nutritionalInfo	energy (kJ/kcal), fat, saturatedFat, carbohydrates, sugars, protein, salt, fiber
ingredients[]	name, percentage, origin, isOrganic
originCountry	Country of origin (ISO 3166-1)
organicCertification	Organic certification reference
harvestDate	ISO 8601 harvest date
storageConditions	Temperature range, humidity, shelfLife

6 Initiative Profiles

Each DPP initiative composes the core with a different set of extensions. The platform defines five profiles:

Profile	Extensions Used	Purpose
Tractus-X Battery	Core + Battery + SoC	Catena-X automotive ecosystem
Battery Pass	Core + Battery + SoC + LCA-EF	Battery Alliance compliance
Core-Only	Core only (no extensions)	Minimal cross-sector DPP
Food Product	Core + Food (optional LCA-EF)	Food/agriculture sector
All Extensions	Core + Battery + SoC + LCA-EF + Food	Testing and demonstration

Table 7: Initiative profiles and extension composition

7 Schema Evolution: v0.1 to v0.2

Aspect	v0.1 (Jan 2026)	v0.2 (Feb 2026)
Architecture	Monolithic, battery-heavy	Product-agnostic core + extensions
Core fields	~68 fields (most battery)	17 fields (product-agnostic)
Domain fields	Embedded in core	~60 fields across 4 extensions
Battery structure	Flat fields	6 nested sub-objects
Vocabulary hosting	Inline	5 OWL ontologies on GitHub Pages
Linked data	Optional	Native JSON-LD 1.1 contexts per module
Product types	Battery only	Battery, food, electronics, any

8 Provenance Model

Per-Field Provenance Tracking (PROV-O Aligned)

The platform attaches provenance metadata to **every mapped field**, documenting source, transformation, timestamp, and confidence. Both JSON and JSON-LD outputs share the same structure through a unified interface.

8.1 Provenance Structure

Component	Type	Description
adapter	Object	Name, version, initiative of the adapter that produced this output
timestamp	String	ISO 8601 timestamp of normalization
fields.{name}	Object	Per-field provenance: <code>source</code> , <code>actor</code> , <code>confidence</code> (0–1), <code>conversion_rule</code>
dataCoverage	Object	<code>score</code> (0–1), <code>populated</code> count, <code>expected</code> count

8.2 Provenance Example

Per-field provenance for `ratedCapacity`

```
{
  "provenance": {
    "adapter": {
      "name": "TractusXAdapterJSON",
      "version": "0.2.0",
      "initiative": "Tractus-X"
    },
    "timestamp": "2026-02-25T14:30:00Z",
    "fields": {
      "ratedCapacity": {
        "source": "stateOfBattery.ratedCapacity",
        "actor": "TractusXAdapterJSON",
        "confidence": 0.95,
        "conversion_rule": "Direct mapping (Ah)"
      },
      "chemistryType": {
        "source": "batteryChemistry.value",
        "actor": "TractusXAdapterJSON",
        "confidence": 1.0,
        "conversion_rule": "Direct string mapping"
      }
    }
  },
  "dataCoverage": {
    "score": 0.83,
    "populated": 10,
    "expected": 12
  }
}
```

9 Gap Reporting

When the adapter cannot fill a field, the platform reports a **semantic gap** rather than silently omitting data:

Gap Category	Severity	Meaning
Missing field	High / Medium	Source data does not include this field
Granularity mismatch	Medium	Source field exists but at a different level of detail
Unit conversion conflict	Low	Numeric value present but unit transformation needed

Gap report example

```
{
  "gaps": [
```

```

{
  "field": "extensions.battery.circularity.recyclingInstructions",
  "reason": "Field not available in Tractus-X data model",
  "severity": "medium",
  "category": "missing_field"
},
{
  "field": "extensions.lca-ef",
  "reason": "Tractus-X profile does not include LCA-EF extension",
  "severity": "low",
  "category": "missing_field"
}
]
}

```

10 Vocabulary Namespaces

All vocabularies are defined as OWL ontologies and hosted via persistent URIs:

Vocabulary	Namespace URI
Core DPP	https://jorgerenatoleon.github.io/DPP-Interoperability-Microservices/vocab/core#
Battery Extension	https://jorgerenatoleon.github.io/DPP-Interoperability-Microservices/vocab/battery#
SoC Extension	https://jorgerenatoleon.github.io/DPP-Interoperability-Microservices/vocab/soc#
LCA-EF Extension	https://jorgerenatoleon.github.io/DPP-Interoperability-Microservices/vocab/lca-ef#
Food Extension	https://jorgerenatoleon.github.io/DPP-Interoperability-Microservices/vocab/food#

11 Discussion Questions Reference

For your reference, these are the main topics we will discuss during Protocol 1. You do not need to prepare answers in advance—we will walk through them together using this handout.

- A1.** Looking at the 17 core fields (Section 4), could your organization fill these fields for a product you work with? Which would be easy, which would be difficult?
- A2.** Thinking about the extension modules (Section 5), which extensions would apply to the products you work with? Are there fields you would need that are not covered?
- A3.** Does the split between product-agnostic core fields and domain-specific extensions make sense for interoperability? Would you structure it differently?
- A4.** If the platform had to support a completely new product type (e.g., textiles), which core fields would still apply and which would need to change?
- B1.** The provenance model (Section 8) tracks where each data field came from. Would organizations in your domain actually use this metadata for compliance or decision-making?
- B2.** When the source data is missing or mismatched (Section 9), the platform flags it as a gap with a severity level. Are the three gap categories sufficient? Are there other types of data issues you encounter?
- B3.** What level of confidence would you need before automatically processing a field vs. flagging it for manual review?

— End of Handout —